

INVESTIGATION ON THE MECHANICAL ROBUSTNESS OF CFRP MOLDS

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ABSTRACT

Molds made from carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have advantages over metallic molds as equal thermal expansion and lower costs. On the other hand these molds have a limited service time for example due to surface wear out. To extend the service times of these molds concepts that reinforce or protect exposed areas in the tool as for example edges need to be developed. The aim of this work is to investigate the parameters that influence the failure of composite edges due to a static load. Therefore a test has been developed that determines a quasi-static strength of edges. Based on this test the mechanical properties of composite edges with different fiber reinforcements and matrix systems are compared. The edge concepts investigated are: an edge filled with the conventional laminate resin, one with a gelcoat reinforced surface, a reinforcement by a roving along the edge, a short fiber reinforcement and an edge with a locally applied elastomeric matrix system. The test show that fiber reinforcements in the edge lead to a higher edge stiffness and strength. The deviation of the results strongly dependent on the distribution of the reinforcing fibers in the edge. Elastomeric edges are a promising concept since no damage occurs at all within the test.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) molds are used for the production of large scale high performance parts as wind turbine blades or shell structures like the thrust reverse system. Compared to metallic tooling materials CFRP molds have advantages such as equal thermal expansion, light weight resulting in easy handling and lower costs [1]. However CFRP molds exhibit a limited operating temperature and short service times due to surface wear out compared to state of the art metal tooling.

This work investigates surface wear out. In this context surface wear out is defined as deformations and break outs at the mold surface. A fragile part of CFRP molds are edges. Usually edges are avoided in composite design. But in mold design edges are sometimes necessary to reproduce the demanded part geometry or to create a continuous surface at the parting plane of for example light RTM tools. A main cause for damaged edges in CFRP tools is fiber pinching. Fiber pinching describes a fiber that is pinched in the parting plane during mold closure. The objective of this work is to investigate the influencing variables determining the failure of composite edges. Based on the results guidelines for the design of composite edges can be derived.

Therefore a testing procedure has been developed determining the quasi static strength of composite edges depending on the material layup and design based on the described application related load cases. The test is based on conventional hardness testing such as Vickers [2] and an edge test for brittle materials [3,4]. In the developed test a flat cylindrical indenter penetrates a composite edge until failure of the edge. Relevant measured variables are the indentation depth [mm], the force at failure [N] and the overlap of the indenter [mm].

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Sample preparation

The edge samples are manufactured by the vacuum assisted resin injection process (VARI) using an aluminum angle section as a mold. The fiber materials are applied in the mold and covered by a peel ply, a flow promoter and a vacuum bag. The infiltration direction is along the profile.

Five different edge concepts are investigated in this work. All concepts are based on the standard fiber layup introduced in the next section with varying material combinations right in the edge.

The reference concept consists of an edge of pure resin since the fabric cannot be draped into the edge completely (concept abbreviation: RH). The second concept is based on a gelcoat that is applied on the mold by a brush and then cures at room temperature for 16 h. After that the standard layup is applied and infiltrated (GC). As a third variant three 50k rovings are applied in the edge to fill it with fibers along the profile. As a quasi-isotropic edge reinforcement short fiber chops are placed in the edge (SF). The fifth concept uses the standard layup with two different resin systems. In a first step a PU elastomer is infiltrated locally at the edge. After curing the first resin system the rest of the layup is infiltrated by the standard epoxy resin. This results in a purely elastomeric edge that is integrated in a carbon fiber reinforced thermoset. Figure 1 illustrates the fiber layup and the different edge concepts investigated.

Figure 1: layup of the edge specimen and the edge concepts investigated

All samples are cured at room temperature. Samples RH, GC, RV and SF are additionally post cured at a defined temperature cycle (60 -180°C in 20 °C steps that are held for 2 hours) given by the material supplier to accomplish the curing reaction in the epoxy and gain the final mechanical performance. Concept EE is post cured at 70°C since the recommended operation temperature of the elastomer manufacturer is beneath 80°C.

2.2 Materials

The materials and layup of the specimen are selected to be as close to the application of CFRP tools as possible. Each sample consists of a symmetric layup of two plies of 0/90° fabric (100 g/m²) and five plies of ±45° non crimped fabric (NCF, 300 g/m²). The fabric is made of a 6k HTS 40 fiber and the NCF of a 12k HTS 40 fiber. As edge reinforcing fiber materials 50 k HTS 40 rovings and 3mm carbon short fibers are used.

The epoxy resin system Huntsman Araldite 8615 with the XB 5173 hardener is used as matrix system. The gelcoat used is a Huntsman RenGel SW 5200. The PU elastomer used is a SIKA Biresin 407.

Table 1 gives an overview of the different concepts and the used materials for each concept. The Fiberlayup and the matrix system is the same for all concepts. Concept EE uses a second elastomeric matrix that is locally applied in the edge.

Concept	Abbrev.	Edge fibers	Edge matrix	Fiberlayup	Matrix
pure resin	RH	-	-		
gelcoat	GC	-	RenGel SW 5200 / HY 5212		
roving	RV	50 k HTS 40	-	[[0/90° fabric] ₂ , [±45° NCF] ₅] _s	Araldite 8615/ XB 5173
short fiber	SF	12k HTS 40, 3mm	-		
elastomer edge	EE	-	SIKA Biresin 407		

Table 1: Concepts and the applied materials

2.3 Sample characterization

The samples are characterized visually by an Olympus SZX 10 microscope. Therefore sections are cut from the samples, embedded in epoxy resin and polished in a subsequent step.

Figure 2 gives a qualitative overview of the different edge concepts. The parameters determined within these micrographs are the edge radius [mm] and leg length of the edge [mm]

Figure 2: Micrographs of the specimen cross sections, magnification x 0.75: a) RH, b) GC, c) RV, d) SF, e) EE and f) illustrating the measured parameters (r: radius, l: leg length)

Figure 2 a) shows transparent pure resin edge with the first two layers of fabric. The light dots within the edge of picture b) are the metallic fillers of the gelcoat. The first layers of fabric are embedded in the gelcoat and therefore gives a good connection of the gelcoat surface and the laminate. Concept RV is shown in Figure c). The homogeneously black edge results from the rovings that point out of the plane. The rovings fill out the whole edge as intended. Compared to concept RV the edge in micrograph d) is textured. The short fiber chops are distributed randomly in the edge and therefore reflect the light depending on their orientation in the polished plane. The edge is filled out by the fiber chops but not as accurate and homogeneously as the roving along the edge.

Figure 2 e) shows the white elastomeric edge. The white flowmarks that can be observed within the fabric show that the elastomer reaches into the fiber layup. A clear transition area between the elastomeric and thermoset matrix can't be detected.

The edge radius and leg length of the edge concepts were measured optically at one cross section for each concept. The values presented in

Figure 3 are therefore exemplary. The radius of the specimens depends on the radius of the aluminum mold. Since the molds used within this investigation are cut from an extruded aluminum sheath the radius are not exact and vary in each batch. The leg length of the concepts varies from 3 to 10 mm. The volume and therefore the leg length of each edge concept is strongly dependent on the concept itself and its manufacturing process. Concept RH and GC are manufactured similarly by draping the layup into the edge and infiltrate it in a second step resulting in a similar leg length. Three 50k rovings are placed along the edge for concept RV, resulting in a constant leg length along the profile. The process of applying chopped fibers in the mold is not precise, leading to a varying leg length along the edge. The manufacturing of concept EE is similar to RH and GC except for the SIKA elastomeric resin that is very different in viscosity. To ensure an infiltration of the edge an infiltration gap between the first layers and the edge was left resulting in a larger leg length compared to RH and GC. To investigate the edge concept the leg length of the concept must at least be as long as the overlap of the indenter which is 1mm (compare chapter 2.4). This requirement is fulfilled for all concepts.

Figure 3: Geometry of the edge concepts: a) edge radius and b) leg length

2.4 Setup for quasi static edge strength testing

The objective of the test development is to define a test procedure that gives quantitative results about the strength of a CFRP edge. In literature the characterization of edges can be found for different material classes. Two examples are given in the following.

Weimer [5] describes a test for CFRP edges. In his case an edge is defined as the cutting edge of a CFRP part. The CFRP part is damaged dynamically by a defined energy and then tested in a three point bending test to observe the loss in flexural strength and stiffness. The value that was conducted with this test characterizes the protection of the part by the edge against impact resulting in in-plane delamination.

Hangl et al. and Almond et al. [3,4] have developed a test for edges of brittle material, e.g. ceramics. In this case an edge is defined as the intersecting line of two sample surfaces. Their test is

derived from conventional hardness tests for metals using a pyramidal shaped indenter that penetrates the material sample. The indenter penetrates the sample at defined distances from the edge until the edge breaks. The force at failure and the distance of the indentation mark from the edge characterize the strength of the edge.

Figure 4: Sketches of the indenters and micrographs of the marks resulting from the a) conical b) cylindrical indenter penetrating a RH sample

Since edges in molds are not cutting edges of parts but intersection lines of two surfaces the test developed within this investigation follows the example of Hangl and Almond [3,3,4]. In a first test series a conical indentation tip is used that penetrates the sample 1 mm from the CFRP edge. The tests did not show a sudden and clear failure of the specimen as shown in Figure 4 a). The conical indenter displaced the surrounding material and did not lead to a chipping failure since the thermoset matrix is not brittle compared to ceramics. In a second test series a cylindrical indenter was used to avoid any plastic displacement of material but initiate a sudden failure and therefore a defined strength value. Figure 4 b) shows the cylindrical indenter and its fracture pattern, which depicts a clear cylindrical matrix chip.

Figure 5: Comparison of the force displacement graphs resulting from a conical and cylindrical indenter

Figure 5 shows the according force displacement diagrams for the reference concept RH. The graph of the cylindrical indenter is increasing almost linearly with a higher gradient than the graph of the conical indenter showing a kind of exponential behavior. The graph of the cylindrical indenter rises until the specimen fails ending with a significant drop in the force displacement diagram. The graph of the conical indenter shows several small drops in the curve resulting from several failures in the specimen. But no final failure with a significant drop occurs up to 500 N, the abortion criterion.

The characteristic of both curves can be explained by the geometry of the indenters. The force response of the cylindrical indenter is predominantly due to the elasticity of the specimen whereas the response from the conical indenter is a mixture of an elastic material behavior and a plastic deformation due to the small surface of the tip. The graph rises exponentially resulting from the increasing surface due to the penetration of the conical tip.

The test developed needs to be relevant for the underlying problem of damaged tooling edges. Any occurring non elastic deformation of the tooling surface leads to an impression in the final part and therefore an undesirable deviation in geometry. So the developed test needs to display a clear first failure of the composite edge. Based on results shown in Figure 5 a cylindrical indentation tip is used for conducting the test series.

Figure 6: Test setup for quasi static edge strength testing

Figure 6 illustrates the setup of the quasi static edge strength test. The center of the test setup is the cylindrical indenter. The indenter is connected by an adapter to a 10 kN load cell which is again connected to the compression test machine. The specimen is fixed and held in position by an aluminum clamping device that is mounted on the bottom socket of the compression test machine. It is positioned in a way that half of the indenter is in contact with the specimen, resulting in an overlap of 1 mm. The sample is marked about 7 mm below the edge, the indenter 3 mm above its contact plane. Both marks are used as reference points for the video extensometer that determines the distance of both marks optically. Like this, the penetration depth of the indenter can be measured independently from any deformation of the machine, all adapters or the clamping device, as well as independently from a movement of the sample in the clamping device.

The test procedure can be divided into two steps. The indentation and the visual characterization of the indentation mark. In the first step the specimen is penetrated by the indenter at a speed of 1 mm/min until a decrease of the force of 20 % after first failure of the specimen. In the second step the position of the indentation marks is determined. Since the specimen can only be positioned with an accuracy of about ± 0.2 mm this is necessary. By referencing the force at failure to the visually determined penetration area an area load at failure is calculated.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 7 shows characteristic area load displacement graphs obtained by the quasi static edge strength test. The curves differ in the gradient at the start of the curve and the type of failure resulting in a characteristic drop of the curve. Looking at the gradient of the curves, the different concepts can be divided into three groups beginning with the steepest incline: the fiber reinforced edges, the thermoset edges and the elastomeric edges. Concept PR, RV and SF show a clear drop in the curve when the specimen fails. Concept RV breaks suddenly and the area load drops to a value lower than 20 % of the maximum. No fibers break when the specimen fails since the fibers are positioned perpendicular to the force. But the bonding of the fibers break, resulting in slipping of the fibers in force direction. After the first drop in the curve of concept SF the curve inclines again in a discontinuous way. At the first drop a first delamination occurs. But in contrast to concept RV the randomly orientated fibers can still carry the load and lead to the second incline of the curve. Concept PR also shows a second peak in the load displacement curve. In that case the failure occurs at the boundary between the pure resin edge and the first layer of fibers. At the first drop a crack occurs at the boundary but the resulting chip still is supported by the layup beneath. At the final decline of the curve the chip slips down the layup and separates from the specimen. Concepts GC doesn't show a sudden failure but a continuous plastic deformation until a final failure. It is assumed that the cracks that occur in the brittle matrix are influenced by metal fillers within the polymer and lead to a kind of ductile failure. Concept EE doesn't break up to a deformation of 1 mm. After returning with the indenter to the starting point, no clear mark can be identified on the specimen. The connection of the elastomeric edge doesn't show any damages as well.

Figure 7: Characteristic area load [N/mm²] displacement [mm] graphs for each edge concept

As mentioned in the previous passage the gradient of the area load displacement graph characterizes the different concepts. Therefore a value w for stiffness is calculated. To ensure a calculation within the linear part of the graph the stiffness is calculated between the displacement of 0 and 0.03 mm (compare Figure 8 a)). Formula 1 shows the equation for w . The range x_0 is fixed to 10 mm since that is the length between the visual markers. That value is not comparable to the free path of tensile tests, since a part of the specimen and a part of the indenter is located in between the markers.

$$w = \frac{\Delta P}{\varepsilon_e} = \frac{P}{\left| \frac{x - x_0}{x_0} \right|} \quad (1)$$

with $x_0 = 10 \text{ mm}$ and $x = 0.97 \text{ mm}$

Each concept has been tested ten times. Comparing the mean stiffness w of Figure 8 b) and taking in account the standard deviation concept RV has a higher stiffness compared to concept GC and PR.

Concept SF has a mean stiffness that is comparable to RV but has a much higher standard deviation. Concept EE has the lowest stiffness due to the elastomer used in the edge.

Figure 8: a) Visualization of the stiffness w in the area load displacement diagram of concept PR, b) mean stiffness and its standard deviation of all concepts

Figure 9 a) gives the mean area load at first failure for all concepts except for EE. The elastomeric edge doesn't fail within the test and therefore is not considered in the analysis and the following interpretation. Again the area load at first failure of RV is higher than the one of PR and GC. The mean area load at failure of concept SF is in the range of RV but with a higher standard deviation.

The results of the stiffness w and the area load P at failure are comparable. Concept PR shows in both diagrams the lowest value (neglecting EE). PR is the reference concept, which represents an edge that is not particularly optimized towards high mechanical surface properties. Concept GC contains a gelcoat which is a resin system that has been customized towards high surface properties as hardness and abrasion. The results show that the gelcoat has a positive influence on the edge strength. On the one hand the mean value of the stiffness and area load at failure goes up at comparable standard deviations and on the other hand the damaged area gets smaller compared to concept PR. Reinforcing the edge by fibers gives the highest values for the stiffness and the area load at failure for the quasi static edge strength test. A roving that is placed in the edge (RV) gives a homogeneous material in the edge resulting in the highest values with comparably little deviation. Short fiber chops (SF) reinforce the edge more heterogeneously resulting in the largest deviations of all concepts within this test. Since the fiber chops are distributed randomly the measured values are strongly dependent on the position of measurement and the local fiber distribution.

Figure 9: a) mean area load and b) mean deformation at first failure of the edge concepts

The concepts do not differ significantly in the mean deformation at first failure shown in Figure 9 b). The values vary from 0.14 to 0.16 mm with standard deviations from 0.02 to 0.04. So no statement about the resistance of the concepts against defined deformations can be made.

4 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

Within this investigation a test for the quasi static strength of edges made out of composite material is introduced. Here an edge doesn't mean a cutting edge but an edge of two surfaces intersecting. Five different edge concepts have been manufactured and characterized by the developed test method: an edge filled with an epoxy resin (concept abbreviation PR), a gelcoat used as a surface reinforcement (GC), a fiber roving placed along the edge (RV), short fiber chops of 3 mm length distributed in the edge (SF) and an elastomer infiltrated in a defined area of the edge (EE). The tests show that fiber reinforced edges are stiffer and have a higher area load at first failure than the unreinforced edges. Furthermore the specimens with more homogeneous material in the edge show a smaller deviation of the results. The concept with the gelcoat applied (GC) and the pure resin edge (PR) show similar results. Both edge concepts are based on epoxy. The gelcoat differs from the pure epoxy resin in hard filler materials that improve the abrasion behavior and surface hardness but according to the results do not influence the strength of edges significantly. Whereas a very different resin system as the elastomer shows a much lower value for stiffness but doesn't fail at all up to a displacement of 1 mm. The choice of an edge concept for a CFRP mold finally depends on the requirements. A stiff fiber reinforced edge results in the best contour accuracy even at high loads on the edge. An elastomeric edge is a promising concept for robust edges with the drawback of contour deviations when loaded during process.

A general questions occurring from the tests is whether the deviations result from the material or the test itself. In this investigation an indenter with a diameter of 2 mm and an overlap of 1 mm was used which is within the magnitude of the width of the fiber chops used to reinforce the edge of concept SF. Here the large deviations result from the position of the indenter that at one point pushed onto a fiber and at another point pushed onto pure resin. To achieve a value that is more robust against inhomogeneous materials and therefore gives smaller deviations in results the size of the indenter will be varied to bigger diameters in subsequent tests. A larger indenter possibly leads to a slurred value describing the mechanical properties of a composite edge with less deviation

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